

Liudmyla HAVRILOVA

*Dr. Hab. in Pedagogics, Professor,
Head of the Primary Education Theory and Practice Department,
SHEI “Donbas State Pedagogical University”,
Sloviansk, Donetsk region, Ukraine*

MUSIC ART AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY: CONCEPTUAL CHANGES OF THE NATURE AND FORMS OF MUSIC EXISTENCE

Abstract. Digital technologies have long entered the sound and semantic space of music, musical art is changing under the influence of digitalization, musical activity is being transformed in response to the development of artificial intelligence. These questions are currently the subject of attention for musicologists, cultural scholars, and representatives of other fields due to the emergence of new creative perspectives for musicians, as well as new aspects of the development of music and musical creativity. The goal of this research is to analyse fundamental changes in the basic elements of music within the aesthetic interaction of composer-performer-listener, caused by the influence of digital technologies.

Key words: musical art, digitalization, sound musical landscape, musical creativity, performance, music perception

Анотація. Цифрові технології давно увійшли у звуковий та семантичний простір музики, музичне мистецтво видозмінюється під впливом цифровізації, у відповідь на розвиток штучного інтелекту трансформується музична діяльність. Ці питання наразі є предметом уваги музикознавців, культурологів, представників інших спеціальностей у зв'язку з формуванням нових творчих перспектив діяльності музиканта, нових аспектів розвитку музики та музичної творчості. Метою дослідження є аналіз принципових змін першооснов музики в межах естетичної взаємодії «композитор – виконавець – слухач», спричинених впливом цифрових технологій.

Ключові слова: музичне мистецтво, цифровізація, звуковий музичний ландшафт, музична творчість, виконавство, сприйняття музики

Relevance. The development of digital technology has significantly changed the nature of many types of art. It concerns music as the art of sounds and a unique informational environment. Since the mid-20th century, the experiments with generating new sounds in the fields of electronic, electroacoustic, and computer music have been conducted. Due to technical devices for processing digital signals, new means of musical expression have become available. Composers (R. Boulez, G. Xenakis, K. Stockhausen et al.) contributed to the emergence of a new synthetic sound space (Boulez & Gerzso, 1988), to the creation of computer systems for interactive composition of musical scores, translating graphical notation into sound waves.

At the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries, the rapid development of information technologies and electronic musical instruments (ranging from basic synthesisers to powerful musical computers) led to the emergence of a new direction in musical creativity – Musical Computer Technologies (MCT). This is a new interdisciplinary area of professional activities related to specialised application software and hardware, requiring knowledge and skills in both the musical and computer science domains.

Forms of musical existence and presenting music to listeners have changed, too. Multimedia, transmedia and virtual musical environment has become integral attributes of contemporary musical practice. In this digital art space, the real and the digital, the artificial and the natural elements become components of equivalent values.

Digital technologies have integrated into music education. Musicians in many educational institutions worldwide are taught the basics of musical programming (Institute for Research and Coordination in Acoustics/Music (IRCAM) in National Georges Pompidou Centre of Art and Culture in Paris (<https://www.ircam.fr/>); Center for Computer Research in Music and Acoustics (CCRMA) Department of Music Stanford University (<https://ccrma.stanford.edu/>); Institut für Musik und Akustik / Hertz-Labor in Karlsruhe and others.

The potential and means of teaching musical art have significantly expanded through the application of computer (digital) learning resources. The collection of simulation software tools for learning to play musical instruments and vocal training, developing a musical ear, and fostering musical creativity is rapidly enriched with new developments.

How do digital technologies function in the sonic and semantic space of music? How does musical art change under the influence of digitisation? And how do musical activities transform as a response to the development of artificial intelligence? These questions are currently the subject of attention for musicologists, cultural scholars, and representatives of other fields due to the emergence of new creative perspectives for musicians, as well as new aspects of the development of music and musical creativity. **The goal of this research** is to analyse fundamental changes in the basic elements of music within the aesthetic interaction of composer-performer-listener, caused by the influence of digital technologies.

Research results. This research presents findings from a review of philosophical, sociological, cultural and musicological literature that presents different aspects of digitalisation of musical art. Theoretical and philosophical basis of research includes modern philosophical trends that demonstrate the evolution of poststructuralism and go beyond its boundaries:

– New materialism, Agential Realism, Speculative Realism (K. Barad (2003), J. Bennett (2010), M. DeLanda (2006)). New materialism in culture theory is connected to the revival of materialistic ontologies, a “turn to matter”. It is a new, complex, and pluralistic phenomenon that involves an interpenetration of the natural and social worlds (new materiality in art). These philosophical views are posthumanistic and postanthropocentric, as the main focus in social research shifts from people to material phenomena. The reconsideration of realism in art emerges in 21st-century art through Agential Realism, Speculative Realism, and Reflexive Realism. It should be regarded as the representation of new objects of reality, as a new procedure for producing a certain alternative version of reality in which technical and artistic contexts are inseparable.

– Object Oriented Ontology (G. Harman (2018), T. Morton (2015)) – intellectual movement in the arts and humanities. For object-oriented ontology (OOO), art is far from a superficial and exclusively human-flavoured region of reality. OOO thinks of art not as decoration, but as the fundamental operation of cause and effect. To make an artwork is to interfere directly with the realm of causes and effects. As Harman writes, “The world is not the world as manifest to humans; to think a reality beyond our thinking is not nonsense, but obligatory.”

– Deep Ecology – a cultural direction of deep ecological perspective that emphasises the interconnectedness and harmony in our universe (Aaron S. Allen & Kevin Dawe (2017)). It highlights the ecological aspects in art. Ecologism is a theme and cultural trend in popular music. Eco- and ethnomusicologists, focusing on the issues of music and the environment, increasingly emphasise the intersection of music and nature, as well as the role of music in ecological activism. Ecomusicology is aimed at studying the intersections of music/sound, culture/society, and nature/environment (ecomusicology as studying the intersections of music/sound, culture/society, and nature/environment).

The analysis of music within the framework of these philosophical and cultural systems allows us to consider music as an evolving ecology; a non-human force that demonstrates real changes in the world. The interconnection between musical activity and various environments in which people live and work, as well as between traditional and digital artistic content, is of significant importance.

Musicological methods include:

- method of immersion in the historical and cultural context;
- synchronic and diachronic methods of musical analysis;
- method of music analysis-interpretation.

Conclusions. The understanding and presentation of significant changes in musical aesthetics, theory, and practice have occurred in the last decade under the influence of digital technologies. These changes have affected three fundamental modes of the existence of music, the so-called composer-performer-listener triad, which constitutes a unified and integral system with an inseparable interconnection and interdependence of its components.

1. Musical creativity. Contemporary compositional practices require proficient computer skills: software for musical notation; new types of notations that exist solely within computer programming; electronic musical creativity exploring new sounds; manipulations with traditional sonic complexes. Experiments with artificial intelligence. Changes in the “sonic musical landscape”.

2. Musical performance. New forms of musical artistry facilitated by the integration of transmedia and multimedia technologies within the context of a holistic philosophical approach. Musical performance creativity as a reflection of socio-psychological changes, tastes, and aesthetic needs of listeners.

3. Music perception. The perception of music (listening activity) as a consequence of changes in the conditions of the performance under the influence of technical-communicative digital tools and a qualitatively new type of interpretation. Contemporary acoustic environment and its ecology.

Digital influences on music education (new generation of digital learning resources, online communication, cloud environments, etc.).

References

- Allen, A. S. & Dawe, K. (eds.) (2017). *Current Directions in Ecomusicology: Music, Culture, Nature*. Routledge.
- Barad, K. (2003). Posthumanist Performativity: Toward an Understanding of How Matter Comes to Matter. *Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, 28(3), 801–831.
- Bennett, J. (2010). *Vibrant Matter: A Political Ecology of Things*. Duke University Press. <https://www.perlego.com/book/1466281/vibrant-matter-a-political-ecology-of-things-pdf>
- Boulez, P. & Gerzso, A. (1988). Computers in Music. *Scientific American*, 258(4), 44–51. <http://articles.ircam.fr/textes/Boulez88c/>
- DeLanda, M. (2006). *A new philosophy of society*. Continuum.
- Harman, G. (2018). *Object-Oriented Ontology. A New Theory of Everything*. Pelican.
- Morton, T. (2015, December 15). *What If Art Were a Kind of Magic?* Art Review. <https://artreview.com/november-2015-feature-timothy-morton-charisma-causality/>